

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WRIGHT****FIRST NAME: SKEETER****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes).
The author did not use Zotero to insert references.
The author did use Grammarly Premium.
The author used the following software: MS Word Office

QUIZ: ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE

1. When citing different types of sources:

- The citation structure differs with different types of sources.¹**
- Books, magazines, websites, and newspapers use the same citation structure.
- The same structure of citation is used for all types of sources.
- Websites are not cited.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

2. **Adu (n.d.) notes what four basic things to think about when writing the methodology chapter of a qualitative dissertation?**

- Previous dissertations that may be related, dates of previous related dissertations, the credibility of dissertations authors, depth of other dissertation's research.
- Proposed length of chapter, citation style to use, range of dates of literature sourced, source of any translations.
- Data, problem, purpose, question.²**
- Need for a chapter on methodology, timeline of completing the chapter, where in the dissertation will the chapter be placed, amount of detail to be included.

3. **The title of a book:**

- Is not italicized in the bibliography.
- Is italicized in the bibliography.³**

² Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* (Los Angeles: National Center for Academic & Dissertation Excellence, n.d.), Video.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 103.

- Is followed by the author's name in a bibliography.
 - May be abbreviated in a bibliography.
4. **Bloomberg and Volpe (2008) authored a book on:**
- Writing for a legal audience.
 - The structure of a quantitative dissertation.
 - Legal document citations.
 - A roadmap to writing a qualitative dissertation.**⁴
5. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe (2008), the structure of a qualitative dissertation should be:**
- Overview, methodology, literature review, analysis of findings, conclusion.
 - Introduction to research problem, literature review, research method, findings, analysis of findings, conclusion and recommendations.**⁵
 - Research problem, methodology, literature review, findings, conclusion and recommendations.
 - Research problem, methodology, analysis of findings, conclusion.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), xv-xvii.

⁵ Ibid. 31.

6. *Blue Book: A Uniform System of Citation* (2013)

- Provides a guide to the structure of legal documents.
- Lists rules that prevail over United States local court document citation rules.
- Lists rules for citations only in legal documents.
- Provides information for citing legal documents in academic and legal documents.⁶**

7. Name two different styles guiding how to cite sources.

- Turabian and Chicago.
- Turabian and APA.⁷**
- APA and New York Times.
- Webster and Oxford.

⁶ Mary Mile Prince, ed., *Blue Book: A Uniform System of Citation* 19th ed. (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 1-2.

⁷ Nathanael Warren, *Managing and Citing Sources Using Microsoft Word* https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=11&v=cXeYWGbY04k&feature=emb_title, (accessed 01/04/2020).

8. **Turabian (2013) is:**

- A review of styles of academic writing.
- A guide to an alternative to the Chicago style.
- The authoritative student resource on “Chicago style.”⁸**
- A history of styles developed for academic writing.

9. **Adu (n.d.) describes the difference between a qualitative and quantitative dissertation as:**

- Qualitative includes making observations and developing a theory.⁹**
- Quantitative includes making observations and developing a theory.
- Qualitative relies on numerical data to form a theory.
- Quantitative collects information, analyzes data, develops a theory.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 10.

⁹ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* (Los Angeles: National Center for Academic & Dissertation Excellence, n.d.), Video.

10. **Bloomberg and Volpe (2008):**

- Recommend writing the abstract first so to provide direction to the dissertation.
- Recommend the researcher for a quantitative dissertation takes an “insider” role so to gain insight of the data.
- Describe the qualitative research paradigm as postpositivist.
- Describe a qualitative research inquiry as including case studies, grounded theories, ethnographies, hermeneutics, narrative inquiry, phenomenology.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 128.

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- Warren, Nathanael. *Managing and Citing Sources Using Microsoft Word*, https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=11&v=cXeYWGby04k&feature=emb_title (accessed 01/04/2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.